

Introduction

The modern idea of purebred dogs means moving away from the tradition of dogs being sold without a pedigree and stricter legal restrictions on dog breeding. We also talk about the growing hype around deliberate crosses between established breeds which we generally refer to as designer breeds. There also has been a growing popularity about the benefits of mixed breeds.

Moreover, we'll also be arguing about the worrying health and behavioural problems with even the newly invented designer breeds.

What we are referring to here as purebred breeds are the effects of man-made selection to create groups of dogs with similar appearance and a defined pedigree.

Development Of Modern Dog Breeding

Firstly, we'll be talking about the concept of traditional Kennel Clubs,

Kennel clubs are organizations that register, promote, and maintain standards for purebred dogs. They keep records of dog pedigrees, set breed standards, organize dog shows, and encourage responsible dog breeding and ownership.

The first Kennel club was established in England in 1873.

Now, we'll talking about the concerns regarding health disorders in purebred dogs.

- 1) **Inbreeding-** The build-up of heritable diseases is a predictable result of increased homozygosity and progressive loss of genetic variation over time in closed breeding populations, no matter the species, due to selection and genetic drift.
- 2) **Breeding for extreme phenotypes-** Extreme conformation in dogs describes a physical appearance that has been so significantly altered by selective breeding away from the ancestral natural canine appearance that affected dogs commonly suffer from poor health and

welfare, with negative impacts on their quality and quantity of life.

- 3) **Insufficiency from Kennel Clubs-** Despite few well-intentioned initiatives, very little real-world change in the health, conformation, or welfare issues of problematic dog breeds appears to have been achieved.

Future of Dog Breeding

Let us now understand about designer breeds and mixed breeds before we move forward towards the present state.

- 1) **Designer breeds-** are dogs produced by intentionally crossing two different purebred dog breeds to combine desirable traits from both parents.

Examples: Labradoodle = Labrador Retriever × Poodle

Puggle = Pug × Beagle

- 2) **Mixed breeds-** are animals (commonly dogs) with ancestry from several different breeds, usually without planned selective breeding.

Example: A street dog with traits of multiple breeds

Now the issue in front of us today is that Newly invented designer breeds and mixed breeds are shown to have important health and behavioural problems too.

Also, some critics of purebred dogs demand an end to breeding and recommend that prospective dog owners rescue dogs from shelters either at home or abroad – the ‘Adopt, Don’t Shop ’mantra. However, in many countries, rescue dogs can only satisfy a small fraction of the wider public demand for dogs. A study in Denmark found that around 2,000 dogs enter shelters each year while the annual number of dogs acquired in Denmark is over 60,000.

Now, let us talk about the way forward; retaining a system of organised dog breeding with formal registers into the future, in my opinion, offers two major advantages compared to uncontrolled dog breeding: traceability and transparency.

This would be in line with some current movement by some national kennel clubs and international organisations to publicly acknowledge that past processes prioritising closed breeding pools and promoting breed standards that encouraged extreme conformation no longer fit with the canine welfare understanding and demands of modern human society.

Most production animal breeding programmes today are based on genetic markers linked to desired traits – so-called genomic selection.

Animal Welfare Implications

The challenge still remains to breed dogs with better mental and physical health.

It is now time for those currently in charge of organised dog breeding to take responsibility for this challenge and to put the health and welfare of the dogs ahead of human goals such as heeding tradition, profit, winning prizes at shows and other outcomes that often

currently are at odds with the well-being of the dogs themselves.

Health and welfare rather than looks should become the new goal in dog breeding.

Conclusion

In this article, I’ve tried to shed light on the modern history of dog breeding techniques and standards.

Although I agree that there’ve been drastic changes in dog breeding field and many have been taken with an intention of their welfare but still as talked above there are a lot of challenges standing tall in front of us.

Hopefully, the changes will take place soon and the factor of human profit starts to hold a lesser value in the equation of dog breeding.